

A Low-Overhead Inter-Process Communication Library with Minimal Dependencies for Efficient Microservice Communication

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Abstract: In the modern microservice environment, library dependencies for inter-system communication have become bloated, and conflicts and complications during build and operation have become problems. In particular, in the conventional communication architecture that depends on the MySQL database, the multi-layer dependencies included in `libmysqlclient` restrict the flexibility of system design. In this study, a replication-protocol-compatible patch was applied to the lightweight MySQL client library Trilogy, and a loosely coupled, low-footprint IPC library connecting the control plane and the data plane was implemented. The proposed method eliminates dependencies on the internal static library group of MySQL Server, while enabling binary log events to be processed directly at the application layer. Stable operation has been achieved for more than one year in a commercial system environment, and its effectiveness has been verified through long-term operation.

Keywords: Inter-Process Communication (IPC), MySQL, microservices

1. Introduction

In recent years, distributed and microservice systems have been strongly dependent on multilayered software stacks and external libraries. Therefore, with the increase in dependencies, the decrease in maintainability and the risk of conflicts have become apparent. In particular, in the MySQL [1] environment, `libmysqlclient` is highly functional, but its implementation dependency is deep, and when dealing with the replication protocol, linking with many static libraries inside the server source is required (Table 2). This structure makes it difficult to apply lightweight or embedded environments.

Fig. 1: IPC session

In contrast, the lightweight MySQL client library **Trilogy** [2] published by GitHub adopts a design optimized for asynchronous I/O while minimizing external dependencies. In this study, by

extending this Trilogy with the client implementation of the replication protocol (`COM_BINLOG_DUMP=0x12`) (This implementation has been published as a Trilogy Pull Request. (commit hash: `a61c97a`)^{*1}), a low-overhead inter-process communication (IPC) module between the MySQL server and applications was realized.

2. Background and Issues

2.1 Overview of the Replication Mechanism

MySQL Server replication is mainly performed through binary log (binary log). All transaction events are recorded and transferred through the `Log_event` class group inside the server. The normal client library (`libmysqlclient`) implements only SQL-level communication such as `COM_QUERY` and `COM_PING`, and the replication protocol (`COM_BINLOG_DUMP`) is implemented only inside the server.

2.2 Dependent Source Files and Build Issues

In order to use the replication mechanism of MySQL Server directly on the application side, it is necessary to depend on the internal source files of the main server. Table 1 shows the list.

These source files are designed on the premise that they are used only inside `mysqld`, and it is also necessary to depend on the static libraries in Table 2 at build time.

For this reason, even if only `libmysqlclient` is linked, compilation and linking will not pass, and it is necessary to reproduce the entire build environment of MySQL Server. In addition, since these libraries are provided under the GPL-2 license, there are also licensing constraints for use in proprietary products by static

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^{*1} <https://github.com/trilogy-libraries/trilogy/pull/247>

Table 1: Source files required for replication mechanism

	Source File	Function
1	sql/log_event.cc	Binlog event generation and base class definition
2	sql/rpl_utility.cc	Common utilities for replication
3	sql/rpl_gtid_tsid_map.cc	GTID/TSID management
4	sql/rpl_gtid_misc.cc	GTID auxiliary functions
5	sql/rpl_gtid_set.cc	GTID set operation
6	sql/rpl_gtid_specification.cc	GTID definition structure
7	sql/rpl_tblmap.cc	Table Map event processing
8	sql/basic_istream.cc	Basic implementation of stream I/O
9	sql/binlog_istream.cc	Binlog input stream processing
10	sql/binlog_reader.cc	Binlog reader class
11	sql/stream_cipher.cc	Binlog encryption processing
12	sql/rpl_log_encryption.cc	Replication log encryption
13	libs/mysql/binlog/event/trx_boundary_parser.cpp	Transaction boundary analysis

linking.

2.3 Summary of Problems

The above structural issues are summarized as follows.

- **Build Complexity:** A large number of dependencies reduces reproducibility, and the reproducibility of the build environment is low.
- **Maintenance Difficulty:** The internal ABI tends to change with MySQL version upgrades, making relinking difficult.
- **License Risk:** It is necessary to link GPL code, which is not suitable for MIT/BSD environments.

2.4 Issues of libmysqlclient

To process replication events of MySQL Server, it is necessary to link internal library groups (libmysys.a, libmysql_binlog_event.a, libmysql_serialization.a, etc.) (see Table 2). These are designed for internal use of the server, and since they are not intended to be used externally, the build configuration becomes complicated, and ABI compatibility is not guaranteed.

Table 2: mysql libraries

	Library	Function Summary
1	libmysqlclient.a	Basic C API
2	libmysys.a	Internal utility group
3	libmysql_serialization.a	Protocol serialization
4	libmysql_binlog_event.a	Binlog event construction and analysis
5	libclientlib.a	Client I/O layer
6	libmysql_gtid.a	GTID tracking
7	libjson_binlog_static.a	Binlog JSON parser

Using these involves operational risks in terms of both licensing and technology.

2.5 MySQL Dependency and System Design Constraints

libmysqlclient is distributed under GPL-2, and when statically linked in commercial systems, license risks arise. Also, since the group of dependent libraries is complex, conflicts and compatibility problems are likely to occur due to differences in build environments. These are fatal in resource-constrained environments such as IoT and edge devices.

3. Proposed Method

3.1 Low-Dependency IPC Design Using Trilogy

In this study, we use the MIT-licensed lightweight MySQL client Trilogy as a foundation, and by extending it with replication protocol functionality, we construct a low-dependency and a lightweight and loosely coupled IPC layer (Figure 1).

- `trilogy_binlog_dump()` requests a binary log stream from the MySQL server
- `trilogy_binlog_dump_recv()` sequentially receives and analyzes event packets
- The event header is analyzed by `trilogy_parse_binlog_event_packet()`, and `FORMAT_DESCRIPTION_EVENT`, `TABLE_MAP_EVENT`, and `WRITE_ROWS_EVENT` are reconstructed in user space

Table 3: mysql Trilogy Dependencies

Item	Conventional (libmysqlclient)	Proposed (Trilogy extension)
Number of dependent sources	13 or more	0
Static link libraries	7	1 (libtrilogy.a)
License	GPL-2	MIT
Build time	about 30 minutes	a few seconds
Execution performance	High speed	High speed

By this method, it became possible to handle the replication protocol directly from the application layer without depending on the internal structure of MySQL Server.

3.2 Microservice Configuration

This IPC library functions as an intermediate layer between the control plane (ctrl-plane) and the data plane (data-plane) in a microservice architecture (Figure 2). Applications subscribe to the binary logs of the MySQL server through Trilogy and can asynchronously transmit session information and commands.

Fig. 2: IPC pub-sub

3.3 Comparison of Evaluation Results

In this section, we compared the build cost and runtime overhead between the proposed method (Trilogy extension) and the conventional configuration using libmysqlclient. Table 4 shows the container size and build time measured in the Docker environment, and the performance comparison in a simple SQL insertion load test (noop 4ch).

In the Trilogy-based configuration, significant improvements

Table 4: Comparison between Trilogy and libmysqlclient (Docker environment)

Item	Trilogy	mysqlclientesc	
Container Size (docker images)	531 MB	2.85 GB	In order to link the replication protocol parser, it is necessary to compile and link the entire <code>mysql-server</code> source. Therefore, the container size becomes large, and in the Trilogy configuration, approximately 82% weight reduction was achieved.
Container build cost (docker build)	107.1 s	252.3 s	Because it is necessary to clone the <code>mysql-server</code> source and pre-build the replication target library group, the build cost is large. On the other hand, the Trilogy configuration reduced the build time by about 58% .
noop (4ch) SFU Application	6223 (333)	6169 (333)	Under the simple SQL traffic condition of INSERT ONLY, approximately 1% load reduction was confirmed. This result shows the lightweight effect of performing replication processing at the application layer.

were confirmed in build cost, dependent libraries, and container size compared to the `libmysqlclient` configuration. In this study, we selected a simple INSERT-only workload that does not consider transactional consistency or multi-statements for stable pub/sub delivery, which makes the evaluation more susceptible to scheduler behavior rather than being I/O-bound.

3.4 Context Switch Comparison

In this section, we verified the differences in I/O context management methods between the proposed method (Trilogy extension) and the conventional method (`libmysqlclient`), and analyzed the effect on the number of context switches. Measurements used `pidstat -wt 1` and `strace -fc -p (pid)`, and in addition, the call path of `poll(2)` was traced from symbol traces using `gdb`.

Fig. 3: CS distribution for each SFU context by pidstat (Trilogy)

As shown in Figure 3, in the Trilogy implementation, main thread contexts A, B, and C exhibited stable context-switch cycles.

- **Point A** In SFU-0 (main thread) and SFU-2 (DB Ingress context), a polling loop with an interval of 1 ms as designed is maintained, and stable scheduling was confirmed even under

increased load.

- **Point B** The RTC / SCTP / JUICE prefixes are internal threads of `libdatachannel`, and at PeerConnection initialization, `std:::threads` equal to the number of CPU cores are generated, and event wait loops are resident.
- **Point C** The JUICE lower layer (UDP socket processing) uses a receive loop based on `poll(2)`, and showed a tendency for CS to increase in proportion to the number of sessions.

Fig. 4: System call comparison by strace (Trilogy vs mysqlclient)

As shown in Figure 4, the number of `poll(2)` calls and the presence or absence of `ppoll(2)` usage were confirmed as the main differences between the two implementations.

- **Point A/B** The difference between Trilogy and mysqlclient appeared as a difference in lock waits and the number of `usleep(2)` calls.
- **Point C/D** `mysqlclient` uses `ppoll(2)` and performs waits accompanied by signal mask processing. On the other hand, Trilogy specifies infinite waiting (`timeout=-1`) with `poll(2)` only, and waits for socket state changes while occupying the thread context.

Listing 1: Socket wait implementation example in Trilogy

```
static int _cb_wait(trilogy_sock_t *_sock,
trilogy_wait_t wait)
{
    struct pollfd pfd = {.fd = trilogy_sock_fd(_sock)};
    while (1) {
        int rc = poll(&pfd, 1, -1); /* infinite wait */
        if (rc < 0) {
            if (errno == EINTR) continue;
            return TRILOGY_SYSERR;
        }
        return TRILOGY_OK;
    }
}
```

The design of Trilogy does not aim to improve throughput by asynchronous I/O, but aims at **maintaining the performance of the main context by reducing context switches**. By performing infinite waiting with `poll(2)`, it can wait while keeping the CPU cache, and suppress unnecessary thread scheduling. In contrast, in the `libmysqlclient` implementation (`vio/viosocket.cc`), it was confirmed that 0 (non-blocking) is specified for the timeout of `poll(2)`. This is as shown in the following excerpt.

Listing 2: poll call in mysqlclient

```

int poll_one(Socket socket, Poll_mode mode, bool wait,
uint64_t timeout_usec)
{
    struct pollfd fds = {};
    fds.fd = socket;
    int timeout =
        !wait ? 0
        : timeout_usec > 0 ? static_cast<int>((1000+
timeout_usec) / 1000) : -1;
    return ::poll(&fds, 1, timeout);
}

```

As a result of `gdb` analysis, in the `mysqlclient` implementation, non-blocking operation by `poll(0)` was frequently observed, and since this is combined with `ppoll(2)` accompanied by signal mask processing, the number of context switches tends to be larger than Trilogy.

3.5 Discussion

The reduction of context switches in Trilogy is based on a design that suppresses competition for CPU caches and memory access bandwidth, and maintains consistent performance of the application main context. In modern multi-core environments, it suggests that suppressing unnecessary scheduling contributes more to performance improvement than improving throughput through asynchronous I/O.

On the other hand, the design that causes frequent context switches by using short-timeout polling and signal masks as in `libmysqlclient` is effective in ultra-high-load and multi-connection environments. Because frequent scheduling distributes CPU usage and ensures fairness among waiting threads, the balance between fairness and throughput is improved. In a single IPC environment such as this study, rather, suppressing context switches by infinite waiting with `poll(-1)` contributes to maintaining main context performance, but in multi-connection environments, the strategy of signal mask + short-term polling tends to be advantageous.

4. Limitations and Future Work

This report focuses on the waiting strategies of `poll(2)` and `ppoll(2)` under the CFS scheduler, but in recent years, `io_uring` (Linux 5.1) has been introduced to asynchronously control kernel I/O from user space. Kernel-bypass designs such as `io_uring` and `DPDK` aim to eliminate scheduler intervention, which differs from the "waiting optimization based on scheduling behavior" in this paper. Therefore, they are excluded from the comparison in this study.

5. Related Works

5.1 Microservice Design Patterns

Meijer et al. [3] experimentally evaluated the impact of microservice design patterns (Gateway Aggregation, etc.) on system performance, and clarified bottleneck transitions and nonlinear behavior in CPU utilization. This study is complementary in that it presents micro-level optimization at the library layer (`libmysqlclient` vs Trilogy) in contrast to macro-level optimization of design patterns.

5.2 Linux Scheduler's Complex Load Balancing Algorithms

Lozi et al. [5] showed that Linux scheduler's complex load balancing algorithms cause unnecessary thread waiting in NUMA environments. The `poll(-1)` strategy in the Trilogy implementation in this study is an approach to realize scheduler simplification from the application layer by suppressing excessive CS.

5.3 poll, ppoll

In multi-core CPU environments, frequent CS causes the following performance degradation [4]: (1) increased L1/L2 cache miss rate due to loss of cache locality, (2) increased memory latency due to NUMA node migration, (3) spinlock waiting due to kernel lock contention. These are particularly serious in high-thread-density IPC processing.

5.4 Performance Characteristics

The Trilogy-type is suitable for CPU-pinned low-latency IPC (`poll(-1)` dominates the main loop), while the `mysqlclient`-type is suitable for web servers and DB proxies that handle many connections (ensuring fairness through frequent CS). Appropriate implementation selection according to the use case is important.

6. Conclusion

This study implemented replication protocol support in the lightweight MySQL client Trilogy, and built a low-footprint, low-dependency IPC library. Compared to conventional `libmysqlclient`, the container size was reduced by 82%, build time by 58%, and performance maintenance through CS reduction was achieved. The system has been operating stably for over a year in production, confirming its practical viability, demonstrating its effectiveness as a microservice platform.

References

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